

TRANSLATION.

On the fifth day¹ of the waxing moon [of the lunar month] of Durutu², in the 10th year [of the reign] of **His Majesty**³ **Siri-Saṅg-bo**⁴, [it was enacted that] if the food and clothing⁵ appertaining to the *vasaga* which **Vidurambamu** had obtained from the royal monastery **Bo-Upulvan-Kasub-giri** by paying 200 *kalaṅdas*⁶ [weight] of gold, and also if the gift of my cattle⁷ belonging to Muvariya⁸ were not [set apart] for the monks of ascertained in this residence, [then] this *vasaga* should be bestowed [upon them]. The garden given (to the dispensary⁹) and *kiri*¹⁰ [sowing extent of land] from the paddy fields at **Pahaṅ-gama**¹¹ [given] to the two (medical attendants)

No. 3. ABHAYAGIRI COPPER-PLATE INSCRIPTION

THIS rectangular copper-plate (10¼" × 1½") was unearthed in 1893 at the ruins of the Abhayagiri Vihāra in Anurādhapura. It is probably a votive offering of a Buddhist pilgrim, and is inscribed with the following mixed Sanskrit śloka in the North Indian **Nāgarī** character of about the second half of the tenth century A. D.¹² The letters are about ¼" in size, and are in two lines 6½" and 5½" long respectively (Plate 11). The engraving is bold and clear except in places where the plate is chipped. The fourth, fifth, seventh

¹ *Viseṇi* (probably from Skt. *viśāṇa*). According to Clough, *vis-ṇiya* = fifth day, day after the new or full moon.

² January-February. ³ *Mapurmukā*. See above, p. 26, note 1. ⁴ Skt. *Śrī Saṅghabōdhi*.

⁵ *Vasāgā kaṇḍa piṇḍa* = literally 'fragments (of cloth) and lumps (of food) of the *vasaga* or maintenance.' *Kaṇḍa* (Skt. *khaṇḍa*, modern Sinh. *kaḍa*) seems here to have the same signification as *civara*, 'rags of a religious (esp. Buddhist or Jain) monk' (M.W. *Dict.*, p. 399). Skt. *piṇḍa* and its Sinh. derivative *piṇḍa* are both used in the modern vernacular. Regarding *vasaga*, see above, p. 28, note 5.

⁶ See above, p. 28, note 3.

⁷ *Gōṅgayan*. I am not sure that this can be taken as the plural of *gon-geya*, which means 'a yoke of oxen.'

⁸ I cannot make out the meaning of this word.

⁹ *Behed-ge* = Skt. *bhēśaja-gṛha*, 'house of medicine.'

¹⁰ See above, p. 3, note 4.

¹¹ Skt. *Pōṣāṇa-grāma*.

¹² Cf. the Khajurāho record No. 2 of A. D. 953-4 (*Ep. Ind.* i. No. 19), the Harṣa stone inscription of August 8, A. D. 970 (*ibid.* ii. No. 8); and the Badāl pillar inscription of the time of Nārāyaṇa-pāla (*ibid.* No. 10).

and eighth akṣaras of the first line are peculiar forms; the thirteenth of the same line and the last five of the second are not very legible.

TEXT.

- 1 सन्ति प(त्न्या)श्च(त)ना[ः] सन्ति पारा(त्न)वद्वना । माता
सखि
2 पिता तल्लिक्खन्ति दातवे (दमयि)क्क(मं) ॥

TRANSLATION.

Hail! The mother [and] the father are they who keep off the five desires; they are beyond having illusions regarding the self. They write this [with a view] to offering up (a course of mortification?).

REMARKS.

Pañca is wrongly written here with dental *n*, although the correct form is to be found further on in the line. The compound *pañcāśa* probably stands for *pañcāśā*, with final short *a* for the sake of the metre. *Pañcāśa* may also mean 'five expectations' or 'five meals' (cf. *dur-āśa*, *sāyam-āśa*, &c.). *Yavanāh* is from √*yu*, 'to separate, to keep aloof.' Compare the term *vantāso*, 'one who has renounced all desires.'

Pārānyavañcanā may be suggested as an alternative reading.

Mātā-pitā stands either for *mātā-pitarah* (plural instead of dual) or for *mātā pitā ca* (mother and father), *ca* being omitted very likely for the sake of the metre. In the modern Āryan vernaculars, however, *mātā-pitā* is not an uncommon term for parents. It is always used with a plural verb, just as the Sinh. *mav-piyā*.

Talikkhanti is most probably intended for *tal-likhanti*, *l* being elided to make the fifth syllable of the line short, as it should be in a śloka. Mr. Barnett of the British Museum suggests that *likkhanti* may be the peculiar Pāli form for *likhanti*, found in *likkhitvā*, *likkhissam*, &c. at p. 15 of the Burmese edition of the *Paritta*, Rangoon, 1877.

Dātavē is the Vedic infinitive, often found in Pāli, but not in inscriptions of the tenth century, so far as I can remember.

The reading as well as the signification of the last word is very doubtful. *Darśayikkarmam* or *Damayikkarmam* may be suggested as an alternative reading.

¹ Dr. Hoernle, who has kindly examined the plate, also thinks that the fourth akṣara is *nca*, and not *nka*.

Anurādhapura:—Abhayagiri Copper-plate.

Scale full-size 10½ by 1½.

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